

Comparative Review of Dengue Fever Surveillance Systems Across South and South-East Asia

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Abstract

Background: Dengue fever remains one of the most significant vector-borne diseases in Southeast Asia, with national surveillance systems playing a central role in outbreak detection, response, and long-term control. Understanding how these systems are organized and where they differ provides insights into their effectiveness and opportunities for improvement.

Objective: This study aimed to compare dengue surveillance approaches in India, Malaysia, and Vietnam with a focus on system design, scope, technology, and performance.

Methodology: A comparative review methodology was applied, drawing on peer-reviewed research articles and official government documents. Indicators included the type of surveillance (case-based, aggregate, sentinel, or entomological), scope of coverage (dengue-specific versus multi-disease), timeliness of data collection and reporting, use of prediction modelling, technology and innovation, as well as stakeholder involvement, strengths, and limitations.

Results: The analysis showed that India operates an integrated multi-disease platform through the Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) and its digital upgrade, the Integrated Health Information Platform (IHIP). Malaysia, in contrast, employs a dengue-specific, legally mandated notification system supplemented by tools such as DenMap, which provide real-time spatial visualization. Vietnam's system is similarly dengue-focused, with recent research demonstrating the potential of predictive modelling to forecast outbreaks one to three months in advance. Common challenges across all three countries include underreporting, limited private sector integration, and the absence of a comprehensive One Health approach.

Conclusion: While each system reflects its national priorities, the comparison highlights opportunities for regional learning: embedding predictive analytics, enhancing data integration, and strengthening multi-sectoral collaboration for more effective dengue surveillance.

Keywords: Dengue Fever, Vector-borne Diseases, Surveillance, Public Health, Health Systems, South Asia, South-East Asia

Introduction

Dengue fever remains a major public health concern across South and South-East Asia (SSEA), a region that is characterized by climatic and environmental conditions highly conducive to the spread of mosquito-borne diseases. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2024), approximately 50% of the global population is at risk of contracting dengue, with 100 to 400 million infections reported annually. The global burden of the disease has increased in recent years, with a significant rise in both geographical distribution (Tsheten et al., 2021) and incidence. Since 1995, the number of countries reporting dengue has tripled, with the disease now present in more than 120 countries worldwide (Colón-González et al., 2023). At the same time, dengue has also been shown to cause a considerable economic burden, particularly in endemic countries (Shepard et al., 2013). This expansion underscores the urgency of addressing dengue not only as a regional issue but as a growing global health threat.

According to the WHO (2024), dengue transmission is most common in tropical and subtropical climates, especially in densely populated urban and semi-urban areas. The disease is primarily spread through the bites of infected female *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes, although *Aedes albopictus* can also contribute to transmission. The virus is transmitted via human-to-mosquito cycles, but maternal transmission has also been reported. Dengue infection may be asymptomatic or mild, but in some cases, it can cause severe and potentially fatal illness. Symptoms of non-severe dengue include high fever, severe headache, retro-orbital pain, muscle and joint pain, nausea, vomiting, swollen glands, and rash. Those who are infected for a second time are at higher risk of developing severe dengue, which can present with abdominal pain, persistent vomiting, bleeding, fatigue, and circulatory failure. In such cases, symptoms can persist for several weeks, causing prolonged fatigue and reduced quality of life (WHO, 2024). For these patients with a laboratory confirmed previous dengue infection, a dengue vaccine is available to prevent a severe second infection. Notably, this vaccine is not recommended to people who have no history of dengue infection, as it may increase the risk of severe infection (CDC, 2025).

Several risk factors contribute to the persistence and spread of dengue in SSEA. Rapid and often unplanned urbanization, combined with population density, human mobility, limited access to clean water, and water storage practices, creates ideal breeding grounds for mosquitoes. Social and behavioural factors – such as community knowledge, attitudes, and practices – also significantly influence exposure risk. In this context, community-based

vector surveillance and control are vital, as they enhance local capacity to detect and respond to outbreaks. Active community engagement has been shown to improve the effectiveness of dengue prevention and response efforts (WHO, 2024).

Given that there is no specific treatment for dengue, and vaccines are only recommended for the prevention of second infections (CDC, 2025), surveillance remains the cornerstone of dengue disease control. Vector control measures, including environmental management, insecticide spraying, and personal protection, are crucial. However, these efforts must be supported by effective surveillance systems, which are essential for early outbreak detection and long-term disease trend monitoring (Runge-Ranzinger et al., 2014). In SSEA, however, significant challenges persist. There is a noted lack of integration between entomological and disease surveillance systems, which can result in delayed or insufficient action. Moreover, many dengue cases go unreported, leading to underestimation of the true burden of the disease in the region (Tsheten et al., 2021).

The example of India shows the growing impact of dengue in SSEA. In 2019, the country reported approximately 157,000 dengue cases and 166 deaths, but in 2024, this number had increased to 233,000 reported cases and 297 deaths (NCVBDC, 2025). This upward trend highlights the need for robust, responsive, and integrated surveillance mechanisms that can capture real-time data and facilitate coordinated response strategies. Currently, however, dengue surveillance in India operates through passive, sentinel, and hospital-based methods, known for their weaknesses, including data reliability, under-reporting, and fragmentary information (Pilot et al., 2020). These limitations are compounded by a lack of human resources and surveillance infrastructure, including diagnostic capacity (Bagcchi, 2015).

Despite the importance of surveillance for the prevention and control of dengue fever, there are few comparative studies on how national dengue surveillance systems are structured and implemented in SSEA countries. Due to the varying disease statistics from routine surveillance of notifiable diseases in endemic countries, a direct comparison of reported dengue cases between individual countries is therefore not possible. This discrepancy results from differences in case definitions, the inclusion of probable cases without laboratory confirmation, varying awareness of dengue symptoms, access to health services, and the availability of diagnostic options (Kim et al., 2025). These differences limit opportunities for cross-country learning and make it difficult to identify best practices that could contribute to more efficient and effective public health measures. Considering this, there is a clear need for

a comparative review of national surveillance systems in SSEA to understand how they differ in terms of design, coverage and performance.

This research seeks to address this knowledge gap by conducting a comparative analysis of dengue surveillance systems across selected countries in SSEA.

The main objectives of this study are to:

1. Identify similarities, differences, strengths, and weaknesses in the structure and implementation of national surveillance approaches.
2. Examine the scope of surveillance systems, particularly whether they focus solely on dengue or are integrated within broader frameworks for infectious disease monitoring.

By addressing these objectives, the research contributes to the Clean Healthy Cities (CHC) Project by supporting informed public health planning and urban resilience through more effective and equitable disease surveillance.

Methods

This comparative review was conducted over a time period of 10 weeks, following a research trip to Bangalore, India. Due to time constraints, the number of documents selected for each country was limited to two or three.

For the literature search, Google Scholar and Google have been searched combining key terms such as “dengue fever”, “disease surveillance”, “vector-borne diseases”, and “dengue surveillance system”. After having identified some relevant research articles, the snowballing principle was utilized to retrieve more literature. This resulted in a solid understanding of dengue fever disease pathology, risk factors as well as prevention strategies. Besides research articles, governmental documents – such as from Ministries of Health (MoHs) – have been explicitly searched for to gather more information about countries’ respective disease surveillance systems. During the search strategy, initially only English literature was considered. This strategy aimed to ensure a focused and comprehensive retrieval of relevant literature to support the review but had to be revised for non-English literature. This was because government documents were often only available in the official language of the country, which was not English. To overcome the language barrier, Google Translator was used.

In consultation with the echo head of research, the Fellow student responsible for the surveillance project as well as considering the discussion with consortia members and experts during the SAGE in-person conference in India, three countries have been selected to be included in this comparative review: India, Vietnam, Malaysia. This selection is based on several factors, including:

- Geographical location in SSEA,
- Similar dengue fever disease dynamics,
- Diverse mix of technological approaches.

The comparative framework designed by last year’s Senior Ambassador (SA) served as a guiding tool to compare the countries’ dengue fever surveillance systems and create an evidence matrix. Since a substantial focus during the development of that previous framework was set on the OneHealth approach in dengue fever surveillance, therefore the tool has been adapted to fit the scope of this research. The indicators have been tailored that they will contribute to answering the research objectives. Therefore, the focus of the original

framework shifted from a OneHealth perspective to assessing similarities and differences, strengths and weaknesses as well as the system's integrity with other vector-borne diseases.

After reviewing scoping reviews and further relevant literature about dengue fever surveillance systems, additional indicators have been included in the comparative framework. Here is an overview of the added indicators and their justification for inclusion:

- **Type of surveillance;** Surveillance systems can be different in their approach, e.g., case-based surveillance collects individual-level data, while aggregate surveillance summarizes total case numbers by groupings like age or location. Passive surveillance relies on routine reporting from health facilities, active surveillance involves actively searching for cases, and sentinel surveillance uses selected sites for detailed monitoring. Finally, syndromic surveillance is based on symptoms, presumptive on clinical diagnosis, and lab-confirmed surveillance on confirmed test results (IDSP, 2020). This indicator was added because the diverse approaches directly influence the level of detail, accuracy, and representativeness of data. This indicator helps distinguish between systems designed for broad situational awareness and those that enable precise, case-level tracking.
- **Scope of system;** Understanding whether a system focuses specifically on dengue or broadly on vector-borne diseases reveals the strategic prioritization and specialization of surveillance efforts. It also helps assess how focused and potentially responsive the system is to dengue-specific trends.
- **Timeliness of data;** This reflects how quickly surveillance data is collected, transferred, analyzed, and acted upon. It is crucial for early outbreak detection and timely intervention. Comparing timeliness helps identify which systems are more effective in preventing large-scale outbreak, as well as for the next indicator.
- **Integration of prediction modelling;** Including prediction modelling for Early Warning and Response (EWAR) indicates a system's capacity to anticipate future outbreaks using data and analytics (IDSP, 2020). This indicator highlights the extent to which systems move beyond reactive surveillance toward proactive forecasting, reflecting innovation and preparedness.
- **Use of technology;** Technology (e.g., digital reporting tools, GIS mapping, mobile applications) enhances efficiency, coverage, and real-time response. Including this indicator shows which countries are modernizing surveillance systems, how such innovations improve performance, and how surveillance data are applied, whether for real-time monitoring, predictive modelling, or operational decision-making.

The original as well as an updated framework for the comparative review can be found in the Appendix A and B.

Results

This chapter describes the findings from the research papers and/or government papers used for this work.

Result from Pilot et al. (2019) - India

The study by Pilot et al. (2019), “The Organization, Implementation, and Functioning of Dengue Surveillance in India – A Systematic Scoping Review”, provides a comprehensive examination of how dengue surveillance has been organized and implemented in India. Conducted at the national level, the review highlights the central role of the National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme (NVBDCP) in guiding policy, and the Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) in coordinating routine reporting and outbreak detection. Surveillance in India is described as primarily passive and sentinel in nature, relying heavily on hospital-based notifications within the public healthcare sector. While some active surveillance takes place during outbreak investigations, the system is largely dependent on routine reports flowing upward from facilities to state and national levels.

The authors note that India’s surveillance framework benefits from its wide coverage and formalized institutional structure, which provides a consistent backbone for national-level monitoring. However, several weaknesses undermine its effectiveness. Chief among these are underreporting, especially from the vast private healthcare sector that remains poorly integrated into formal reporting mechanisms, and fragmentation in data streams across different programme levels. Structural inefficiencies also slow down the flow of information and feedback loops, limiting the system’s responsiveness despite outbreak reports generally being submitted on time.

Notably, the review finds no evidence of One Health approaches, predictive modelling, or the use of advanced technology within India’s dengue surveillance system at the time of study. This leaves a gap in innovation compared to emerging global practices. Nevertheless, the system has shown gradual improvements in case detection and reporting capacity, suggesting that institutional reforms are having some effect. Pilot et al. identify opportunities for better coordination across reporting levels, stronger inclusion of private sector data, and investment in surveillance infrastructure. They argue that while India’s

dengue surveillance system is broad and well established, it remains constrained by outdated structures and has yet to fully embrace digital or cross-sectoral innovations that could transform its capacity to detect and respond to outbreaks (Pilot et al., 2019).

Results from Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) (MoH and Family Welfare, 2020) - India

The IDSP conducts surveillance through three main streams: syndromic, presumptive, and laboratory-confirmed reporting. Syndromic surveillance is carried out by peripheral health workers and community-level staff based on clinical patterns. Presumptive surveillance is conducted by medical officers at PHCs, CHCs, medical colleges, and sentinel hospitals, and they are relying on clinical examinations and presumptive laboratory tests. Laboratory-confirmed surveillance requires appropriate confirmatory laboratory testing to validate suspected cases. Additionally, the programme incorporates passive, active, and sentinel surveillance methods. Passive surveillance depends on routine reporting from health facilities, while active surveillance is undertaken during outbreak investigations or eradication efforts. Sentinel surveillance is carried out in selected hospitals or laboratories to provide more detailed and higher-quality information.

IDSP is a multi-disease surveillance programme covering epidemic-prone conditions across vaccine-preventable diseases, vector-borne diseases, waterborne diseases, respiratory diseases, and zoonotic diseases. Dengue is included under the vector-borne category, alongside chikungunya, malaria, and Japanese encephalitis. Other diseases under IDSP surveillance include for example: cholera, diarrhea, hepatitis A and E, influenza, scrub typhus, anthrax, leptospirosis, and others. Surveillance of COVID-19 has also been incorporated as part of special surveillance.

The routine reporting follows a weekly cycle from Monday to Sunday. Data is to be submitted to the district by the following Monday, then entered into the portal by Wednesday, and considered “in time” if uploaded before Thursday of the following week. Outbreaks or unusual events are required to be reported immediately (within 24 hours) through district surveillance units. Monitoring of timeliness, completeness, and consistency is conducted using indicators and targets (e.g., >80% timeliness) at district, state, and central levels.

The IDSP manual outlines an EWAR framework based on indicator-based surveillance (IBS) and event-based surveillance (EBS). IBS collects structured data from health facilities and laboratories, while EBS relies on unstructured and informal sources such as media, community informants, and rumor reporting. The two are combined under

epidemic intelligence to detect abnormal occurrences or early warning signals. The system uses threshold analysis and trends for outbreak detection.

The IDSP has been upgraded with the Integrated Health Information Platform (IHIP). The IHIP introduces case-based, near real-time reporting with advanced features including geo-tagging, GIS dashboards, automated alerts, integration across disease programmes, and mobile applications for frontline workers. Compared to the earlier IDSP portal, which relied on aggregate weekly data, the IHIP provides disaggregated real-time data with stronger visualization and monitoring tools.

Result from (Draidi et al., 2025) - Vietnam

The preprint by Draidi et al. (2025) explores the use of predictive modelling for dengue surveillance in the Mekong Delta region of Vietnam, where dengue is a highly endemic public health concern. Rather than focusing on the national architecture of the surveillance system, the study demonstrates how routine case-based data from existing reporting channels can be transformed into a forecasting tool that provides advance warning of outbreaks. The authors compiled district-level dengue case reports and combined them with sociodemographic and environmental variables to construct an ensemble modelling approach. This included spatiotemporal methods, supervised principal component analysis, and semi-mechanistic frameworks.

The modelling system achieved promising results, with the ability to forecast dengue outbreaks up to three months in advance, reaching an accuracy of around 69% when predicting outbreaks on that horizon. While not explicitly framed as a One Health approach, the integration of environmental and demographic variables gives the analysis an ecological dimension, extending beyond purely clinical reporting.

In terms of stakeholders, the work was carried out by researchers in collaboration with public health authorities who provided surveillance data, but the intended beneficiaries are provincial and district health offices responsible for outbreak preparedness and response. The study acknowledges several limitations, including the reduced accuracy of predictions in years with unusual seasonal patterns, and the fact that modelling depends on the completeness and reliability of the underlying surveillance data.

Nevertheless, the paper demonstrates a major strength and opportunity. It shows that routine surveillance data can be repurposed into a forward-looking early warning system that translates retrospective case counts into actionable lead time for outbreak control. If

embedded into routine practice, such a system could significantly enhance Vietnam's dengue preparedness, shifting surveillance from a reactive function to a more anticipatory public health tool (Draidi et al., 2025).

Results from (April, 2024) – Vietnam

This Master's thesis, authored by Jennifer April in 2024 and publicly available, is titled "*Dengue Fever in Vietnam: Epidemiology, Challenges, and Strategies for Control*" and focuses on the national context of dengue fever in Vietnam. While the paper does not explicitly adopt a One Health framework, it recognizes the influence of environmental and socio-economic factors – such as climate change, urbanization, and local community conditions – providing an ecological perspective on disease transmission.

The study describes a national, government-led surveillance system that primarily relies on case-based reporting of dengue patients and event reporting during outbreaks, complemented by vector surveillance and control activities. Though largely dengue-specific, the system is discussed within the broader context of Vietnam's communicable disease control programs. Timeliness of data is emphasized as a strategic priority, highlighting the importance of rapid reporting and outbreak response, but no specific reporting timelines are provided. Predictive modeling is not currently integrated into the official system, though the paper suggests that climate-linked and analytic forecasting tools could strengthen future surveillance. Technological applications mentioned include integrated vector management and vaccine research, with potential for digital innovations, though detailed descriptions of current reporting platforms are not included.

Key stakeholders in dengue control include the Vietnam MoH, national public health authorities, healthcare providers, local communities, and international partners such as the WHO and research collaborators. The paper identifies several challenges, including persistent vector management burdens, strain on healthcare infrastructure, socio-economic disparities affecting disease spread, climate change impacts, and difficulties in sustaining policy implementation and community engagement. At the same time, it highlights strengths and opportunities, such as strong government commitment, ongoing community education campaigns, expanding international collaborations, and future potential to integrate predictive modeling and digital tools into existing systems.

Overall, the thesis is broad and policy-oriented, focusing on strategic challenges and opportunities rather than technical system mechanics. It underscores Vietnam's recognition of

dengue as a major public health concern and emphasizes the need for innovation in surveillance and disease control (April, 2024).

Results from (Keat-Chuan Ng et al., 2023) - Malaysia

This peer-reviewed research article, authored by Keat-Chuan Ng et al. in 2023 and available through PubMed, is titled “*Dengue Surveillance and Predictive Analysis in Ipoh, Malaysia*”. The study focuses on dengue surveillance at the city level in Ipoh, Malaysia and analyzes eight years of dengue surveillance data (2012–2019) from the city. Over 18,000 reported cases were reviewed, making this one of the more substantial city-level analyses of dengue in the country. While the paper does not explicitly adopt a One Health framework, it incorporates environmental and socio-economic variables such as weather patterns and land use into its analysis, providing an ecological perspective on dengue transmission.

The study analyzed data from the MoH’s e-Dengue system, a dengue-specific, case-based, passive surveillance platform that continuously collects incidence reports. The surveillance system is primarily dengue-focused and, in this study, applied to a single city, though the authors demonstrate its potential for broader predictive applications. Although reporting timeliness is not explicitly discussed, the assembly of an eight-year dataset with over 18,000 cases points towards a steady and continuous flow of information about cases.

A key feature of the study is its integration of prediction modeling. By combining routine case notifications with meteorological and socio-environmental data using GIS and statistical modeling, the authors highlight how routine surveillance can be enhanced for outbreak forecasting. The technological component is strong, as it incorporates geoinformatics, GIS mapping, weather data integration, and analytic modeling to strengthen the understanding of dengue dynamics.

Key stakeholders include the Malaysia MoH and local health officials, who provided and maintained the data, and researchers who conducted the analytic work. The study identifies several limitations and challenges, including its narrow geographic focus on a single city and the absence of discussion about underreporting or contributions from the private sector.

Despite these limitations, the study highlights the strengths and opportunities of Malaysia’s e-Dengue system. The dataset’s large size and organized structure allow for detailed analysis, and the integration of environmental data demonstrates the system’s potential for predictive surveillance at a larger, potentially national, scale.

Overall, the paper illustrates how routine surveillance data can be leveraged for strategic purposes, emphasizing the value of combining traditional case reporting with environmental and technological tools to enhance outbreak prediction and public health decision-making (Keat-Chuan Ng et al., 2023).

Results from (Rizwan et al., 2018) – Malaysia

The study by Rizwan et al. (2018) presents DenMap, a geospatial dengue surveillance system developed in Malaysia. This article describes a web-based platform designed to visualize both notified and registered dengue cases across the country. The system primarily focuses on human health data and does not incorporate a One Health approach.

The DenMap extends traditional surveillance by providing spatial insights into the distribution of cases, although it does not fit into the traditional passive, active or sentinel categories. It relies on two main databases: 1) e-Dengue, which contains registered cases with latitude and longitude information, and 2) e-Notifikasi, which contains reported cases that have been batch geocoded for spatial mapping. Users can filter the data by notification or registration date to get a comprehensive overview of the distribution of dengue cases.

One of DenMap's key strengths is the timeliness of data; it provides real-time visualization of cases, enabling rapid identification of hotspots and trends, which supports swift public health decision-making. The system does not integrate predictive modeling, but it makes great use of technology and innovation, leveraging a package for interactive geospatial visualization in a number of softwares such as R, HTML, JavaScript, and Google Maps.

As the main stakeholders, public health authorities and epidemiologists, who can use the system without requiring technical expertise, have been identified. Challenges include the dependency on the quality and consistency of source databases, potential difficulties in integrating data from multiple sources, and limited scalability outside Malaysia without modification. Strengths include a user-friendly interface, real-time situational awareness, and potential for expansion to other diseases or regions. Overall, DenMap demonstrates how innovative digital tools can improve disease surveillance and response, offering valuable insights for enhancing dengue monitoring systems (Rizwan et al., 2018).

Results from MoH Malaysia (2015) – Malaysia

The “*Garis Panduan Pengawalan Nyamuk Aedes di Tapak-Tapak Binaan (Semakan 2015)*”, issued by the Malaysian MoH focuses on surveillance and control of *Aedes* breeding sites in construction areas, because they have been identified as persistent hotspots for dengue transmission. This document was only available in the local language and had to be translated before analysis.

The guideline emphasizes environmental and entomological monitoring. Developers and contractors are legally required to conduct weekly inspections, eliminate breeding sites, and engage licensed pest control operators where needed. Non-compliance will lead to immediate enforcement measures, ranging from fines to suspension of construction activities.

The guideline represents a regulatory extension of Malaysia’s dengue surveillance system into high-risk environments. Its strengths include strong legal backing under national infectious disease laws, clearly defined roles for both public authorities and private stakeholders, and collaboration with agencies such as the Department of Occupational Safety and Health (DOSH) and the Construction Industry Development Board (CIDB). Nevertheless, challenges persist, as surveys consistently find high levels of *Aedes* breeding in construction sites despite repeated enforcement efforts, indicating that reliance on compliance is not always sufficient. The document does not integrate predictive modelling or digital reporting, but the structured, multisectoral framework provides opportunities for linking entomological data to broader national surveillance platforms in the future.

Discussion

The comparative analysis of dengue surveillance systems in India, Malaysia, and Vietnam highlights both shared characteristics and important differences in their design and implementation. In terms of similarities, all three countries rely on routine, case-based reporting as the backbone of their surveillance efforts. Whether through India’s IDSP, Malaysia’s e-Dengue/e-Notifikasi, or Vietnam’s national reporting system, health facilities remain the primary source of case notifications. Each country has also made efforts to enhance the value of routine data through digital innovation, spatial mapping, or predictive modelling. Despite these advances, underreporting is a persistent problem across all settings, particularly from the private sector or community cases that do not reach health facilities.

Another common feature is the limited adoption of a One Health perspective. While environmental and socio-economic variables are sometimes considered, none of the systems explicitly integrate animal, environmental, and human health data into a unified framework (Draidi et al., 2025; IDSP, 2020; Keat-Chuan Ng et al., 2023; Pilot et al., 2019; Rizwan et al., 2018).

Important differences emerge in the scope and innovation of these systems. India's IDSP is a multi-disease surveillance programme, with dengue included alongside other epidemic-prone conditions. Its strength lies in wide national coverage and a formalized institutional structure, but it is weakened by fragmented reporting and uneven state capacity. Malaysia, in contrast, operates a dengue-specific system, supported by strong legal requirements for 24-hour notification and enhanced by digital tools such as DenMap. This narrow scope enables timely, targeted responses, but the system remains largely passive and still needs to integrate predictive elements. Vietnam falls somewhere in between: dengue is a priority within national communicable disease surveillance, but the most innovative advances are found in research-driven predictive modelling rather than routine practice. The paper from the Mekong Delta shows how existing case data can be transformed into actionable early warning, but this capacity is not yet embedded into national operations (Draidi et al., 2025; IDSP, 2020; Keat-Chuan Ng et al., 2023; Pilot et al., 2019; Rizwan et al., 2018).

Taken together, the findings suggest that while India provides a model of integration and scale, Malaysia demonstrates the advantages of a focused, legally enforced dengue-specific system, and Vietnam illustrates the potential of predictive analytics to shift surveillance from reactive to anticipatory. Each approach carries strengths and weaknesses, and collectively they point to opportunities for cross-country learning. India could benefit from embedding more technology and predictive capacity into its broad system, Malaysia could expand beyond passive notification to incorporate forecasting, and Vietnam could institutionalize its modelling work into national practice. More broadly, all three countries would gain from improving private sector integration, addressing underreporting, and moving toward more holistic, One Health-informed frameworks. Further research is urgently needed to explore these opportunities in depth and inform public health policy-makers.

This review also has several limitations that require discussion. For Vietnam, no government guideline or policy manual was included in this work, and across all countries the evidence base is limited to two or three core papers per setting. This substantially constrains the comprehensiveness of the comparison as well as the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, since some papers are up to ten years old, this further limits the

findings' transferability and requires complementary research to validate and update findings, if necessary.

At the same time, there are important strengths of this work. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first comparative review of dengue surveillance systems across these three countries, and even at the regional level of SSEA. Moreover, the analysis applied a diverse set of indicators, including the integration of a One Health-informed framework, which helps to broaden understanding beyond traditional case reporting. Moreover, the outcome framework adapted for this work is replicable and could be applied in future studies.

Taken together, each country's approach carries strengths and weaknesses, and collectively they point towards opportunities for cross-country learning. India could benefit from embedding more technology and predictive capacity into its broad system, Malaysia could expand beyond passive notification to incorporate forecasting, and Vietnam could institutionalize its modelling work into national practice. More broadly, all three countries would gain from addressing underreporting, and moving toward more holistic, One Health-informed frameworks.

Conclusion and Future Directions

This comparative review of dengue surveillance systems in India, Malaysia, and Vietnam highlights the diversity of approaches within SSEA, reflecting differences in scope, innovation, and capacity. India's IDSP demonstrates the benefits of a broad, multi-disease platform with extensive national coverage, yet faces challenges related to fragmented reporting and limited technological integration. Malaysia illustrates the advantages of a focused, legally enforced dengue-specific system, strengthened by digital tools such as DenMap, which enhance real-time situational awareness. Vietnam shows the potential of predictive modelling to transform routine case data into early warning systems, although such innovations are largely limited to research settings rather than embedded in national practice. Across all three countries, persistent issues such as underreporting, especially from the private sector, and the limited adoption of One Health-informed approaches highlight areas for improvement.

Looking forward, there is significant scope for cross-country learning and system strengthening. Future research should focus on evaluating the effectiveness of these innovations, exploring scalable technological solutions, and developing evidence-based

guidelines for integrating predictive analytics and One Health principles into national dengue surveillance systems. This would help enhance regional preparedness and response to dengue outbreaks and contribute better health outcomes.

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Appendix

A: Original Comparison Framework from Velde et al., 2024

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14190563>

	Study X <i>Insert [Reference]</i>
Title	
Study Location	
One Health integrated in surveillance	
Description of One Health	
Stakeholder	
Integration of Human Health data	
Integration of Animal Health Data	
Integration of Environment Health Data	
Integration of all Three	
Challenges	
Opportunities	
Other Comments	

B: Updated Comparison Framework

	Country 1		Country 2		Country 3	
Type of Document						
Title						
Author and Year						
Study Location						
One Health integrated in surveillance						
Type of Surveillance						
Scope of System						
Timeliness of Data						
Prediction Modelling						
Use of Technology						
Stakeholders						
Limitations/ Challenges						
Strengths/ Opportunities						
Other Comments						